

The method is very fast as compared to other methods^{1, 6}.

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Detection and Determination of Phosphate Using Monomethyl-*p*-Amidophenol as Reagent

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MOST of the methods available for the detection and determination of phosphate are indirect involving complexation of phosphate with molybdenum(VI) and subsequent reduction of the phosphomolybdate. The reagents used for the detection of phosphate are ammonium molybdate and benzidine¹, *o*-dianisidine molybdate and hydrazine², quinolinium molybdate³ and ammonium molybdate and triphenyl methane dyes^{4, 5}. The reducing agents used for the development of the blue colour are tin(II) chloride⁶, hydroquinone⁷, hydrazine sulphate⁸, ascorbic acid⁹ and 1,2,4-aminonaphthol sulphonic acid¹⁰. A few other methods, involving extraction of the blue colour

into an immiscible organic layer are also reported. Very few reports are available for direct detection and determination of phosphate.

The method for detection and determination of phosphate reported in this communication, is a simple and direct one. The phosphate in solution, on reaction with monomethyl-*p*-amidophenol in 1-5 *N* HCl or in 1-10 *N* H₂SO₄, will oxidise it to purple-red *p*-N-methylquinone. The absorption spectrum of the purple-red coloured solution gives maximum absorption at 525 nm.

Materials and method :

Standard phosphate solution : 0.2197 g of potassium dihydrogen phosphate (previously dried at 110° for 1 hr and cooled in a desiccator) is dissolved in deionised water and diluted to 1 litre in a volumetric flask. 1 ml of this solution contains 0.05 mg P.

Monomethyl-*p*-amidophenol solution : 0.05 *M* solution is prepared by dissolving 17.190 g of the reagent (AnalaR grade) in 1 litre deionised water and standardised vanadometrically¹¹.

All other reagents used are of AnalaR grade unless otherwise mentioned.

Beckmann-26 spectrophotometer with auto recorder is used for spectral measurements.

Experimental

Detection of phosphate in a test tube : 0.5 ml of the test solution is taken in a test tube and 0.5 ml of monomethyl-*p*-amidophenol reagent solution is added followed by 1.5 ml of 2.5 *N* HCl. A purple-red colour develops immediately on shaking the test tube which indicates the presence of phosphate.

Limit of detection—2.63 µg/2.5 ml

Limit of dilution—1 : 2,000

Detection of phosphate on a spot plate : 0.04 ml of the test solution is taken in the cavity of the spot plate. 0.04 ml of the reagent followed by 0.04 ml HCl (1 : 4) are added and mixed with a glass rod. An immediate purple-red colour, stable for 48 hr indicates the presence of orthophosphate.

Limit of detection—0.53 µg/0.12 ml

Limit of dilution—1 10,000

Photometric determination of phosphate : To a known volume of the sample solution containing 4-13 µg of P in a 10 ml volumetric flask are added successively 3 ml of 0.05 *M* monomethyl-*p*-amidophenol and 1 ml of conc. HCl. The volume is made up to the mark with distilled water. The absorbance of the purple-red coloured solution, the oxidation product of the reagent, is measured at 525 nm against a reagent blank.

Typical results are presented in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

By preliminary experiments it is found that the acidity should be in between 1-5 *N* for HCl and

TABLE 1—SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC DETERMINATION OF PHOSPHATE USING MONOMETHYL-*p*-AMIDOPHENOL AS REAGENT

Sl. No.	Sample	Taken	P in μg found*	Standard deviation
1.	Na_2PO_4	4.9274	4.9280	± 0.01591
2.	Na_2HPO_4	8.2125	8.2128	± 0.01190
3.	Na_2HPO_4	9.0652	9.0695	± 0.01307
4.	$(\text{Ca})_3(\text{PO}_4)_2$	11.3879	11.3883	± 0.02901
5.	NPK fertiliser	10.6433	10.6436	± 0.02273
6.	NPK fertiliser	6.5261	6.5264	± 0.00702

* Average of five readings.

1-10 N for H_2SO_4 . Below 1 N the colour development is rather slow and above 5N (10 N for H_2SO_4) the colour developed gets discharged. HCl medium is preferred to H_2SO_4 as the colour developed in H_2SO_4 medium is less stable due to the heat developed in the mixing process. The oxidation of the reagent to *p*-N-methylquinone takes place readily in acid medium. It is observed that the colour attains maximum intensity within 5min after mixing the reagent and remains stable for 48 hr, if the reductant is in excess.

The reagent prepared in distilled water is stable for 4 hr. The stability can be enhanced up to 10 hr if preserved in ambered coloured bottles. On prolonged preservation a brownish-red colour develops in the reagent solution due to aerial oxidation and this interferes in the process of oxidation by phosphate.

It is found that chloride, bromide, sulphate, metaborate, thiocyanate, silver(I), gelatin, *p*-hydroxyglycine, acetone, hydroquinone, iron(II), tin(II), arsenic(III), triphosphates or tetraphosphates do not interfere in the said conditions, but dichromate, cerate, quinones, citrate, oxalate, sulphite and bisulphite interfere seriously.

Fig. 1. Absorbance spectrum of oxidation product of monomethyl-*p*-amidophenol with phosphate.

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